

Some Aspects of Uptake of Cobalt by Calcium Hydroxylapatite and Effect of Such Incorporation on the Solubility of the Bone Mineral

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The uptake of cobalt by the synthetic and natural calcium hydroxylapatite is facilitated by (i) increase in Co^{2+} ion concentration, (ii) decrease with the increase of the particle size of calcium hydroxylapatite, (iii) decrease in pH in the range 5.0 to 8.0 of the medium of exchange and (iv) increase with increase of the period of equilibration. Adsorption of Co^{2+} and its accompanying diffusion in to the interior of the crystals explain the mechanism of exchange. The solubilities of solid solutions of calcium cobalt hydroxylapatites determined in the pH range 5.0 to 8.0 decrease with increase in pH of the dissolving medium. This is due to the dissolved phosphate ions function as proton-acceptors and being salts of weak acid undergoes hydrolysis in aqueous media.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ is the primary crystalline inorganic component of human skeletal system^{1,2} amounting to about 40 per cent by weight. It is isomorphous with the naturally occurring mineral known as fluorapatite, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{F})_2(\text{Fap})$. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions which are of biological and physico-chemical significance and in view of its action on calcified tissue is interesting. The $\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{F}^-$ substitution functions as the basis for the prophylactic action of fluorine in the occurrence of dental caries. Environmental pollution due to some poisonous divalent cations is increasing in recent times. The divalent cations from the environments get incorporated into the human skeletal system leading to poisoning and the consequent metabolic effect. The problem of incorporation of Cd^{2+} or Mn^{2+} or Mg^{2+} or Zn^{2+} or Fe^{2+} or Cu^{2+} or Co^{2+} (The cations whose ionic radii are less than that of calcium) into human skeletal system is not thoroughly investigated as is evident from the literature and hence the present work has been undertaken. The replacement of $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{2+}$ results in the formation of solid solutions of calcium-cobalt hydroxylapatite and cobalt hydroxylapatite, $\text{Co}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, which is a product obtained by complete replacement of calcium by cobalt according to the following equation:

The ionic radii³ of Ca^{2+} (0.99 Å) and Co^{2+} (0.74 Å) are close enough together so that it would

not be surprising if solid solutions could be formed between isomorphous substances containing these ions.

The present communication deals with investigations of the dependence of such uptake of cobalt by CaHA and the effect of such incorporation on the solubility of the bone mineral. In addition, the studies were extended to natural hydroxylapatite obtained from human bone and teeth.

Experimental

The details of preparation and identification of CaHA , CoHA and a series of their solid solutions were reported elsewhere^{4,5}. The natural sample was obtained by heating adult human bone and teeth to 900° in a muffle furnace for ~24 hr to remove the volatile constituents. The resulted brittle lumps were powdered and sieved to the required particle size. Chemical compositions (calcium and phosphorus) of these samples were determined by complexometric procedure.

The dependence of uptake of cobalt by calcium hydroxylapatite (synthetic and natural) on factors like

- (i) pH in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0,
- (ii) concentration of Co^{2+} ion in the range between 0.01 M to 0.1 M of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$,

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- (iii) the particle size between 60 mesh to 350 mesh (BSS) were thoroughly investigated and
- (iv) the period of equilibration required for the attainment of saturation of the exchange was determined through kinetic studies.

Glass containers were found to be unsuitable for placing the system due to interference by the dissolution of their ingredients. Potassium hydrogen phthalate-sodium hydroxide and sodium diethyl barbiturate-hydrochloric acid were used as buffer combination of the medium of equilibration. The pH was measured with a line operated Beckman zeromatic pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy.

The buffer solutions were prepared in 0.165M solution of sodium chloride as solvent to simulate the biological conditions and to maintain the activity coefficients of the dissolving species of apatites effectively constant. 0.2 g of 200 mesh (BSS) of CaHA (synthetic and natural) was equilibrated at physiologically important temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ with a solution of 100 cm³ of Co(NO₃)₂(AR) by shaking mechanically in air tight polyethylene containers, changing the factors effecting the uptake under investigation each time while the other factors were kept constant. In an another experiment carried out to demarcate the different steps of exchange process, the reaction mixture was refluxed at 100° under a given set of experimental conditions. At the end of the desired period of equilibration the content was filtered through an IG₄ crucible. The residue was washed thoroughly with redistilled water until it was free from adsorbed Co²⁺ and the calcium and cobalt content of the residue was determined.

A knowledge of the solubility for hydroxylapatite is of extensive importance for undertaking the physiology of bone from the point of view of calcification and resorption. In addition, considerations of the occurrence of dental caries and the protective action of fluorine are based on the information about the solubility of hydroxylapatite. Such solubility studies have additional utility in soil chemistry to account for the action of phosphate containing fertilizers. The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro-analytical determination of phosphate^{6,7} in the solutions of the samples. The apatites get colloiddally dispersed in their aqueous solutions due to their low solubilities and minute particle size. To test for efficient separation of the colloidal component the suspensions of a series of saturated system of CaHA were filtered through an IG₄ sintered glass crucible (particle size retention, 5-10 μ) and phosphorus contents of the filtrates compared with those of the corresponding filtrates obtained through a millipore filter (pore~size 10 μ) fitted to a filter-holder attached to a hypodermic

syringe. The phosphorus contents of the two filtrates were within limits of experimental error (± 0.02 wt%). Extraneous ions dissolved out to the momentary contact of the colloidal suspensions with the glass crucibles were found to be too low to affect the accuracy of the subsequent analyses. Each system shaken mechanically at a regulated speed was set up by adding 0.2 g of 200 mesh (BSS) solute to 100 cm³ of the buffer solution prepared in Co_a-free redistilled water. The systems were placed in air-tight polyethylene containers to exclude the presence of carbon dioxide to avoid thereby alteration in the pH of the dissolving medium and to prevent the formation of carbonato-apatites. The assembly was kept in a thermally insulated cabin maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ to simulate biological conditions. The period of equilibration required for the attainment of saturation was determined through dissolution kinetics as described earlier⁸ and maintained at 3 hr for all the systems. A few ml each of chloroform and toluene were added to the stock solution as well as to systems to eliminate bacterial growth. The systems were separately filtered through IG₄ crucible and the phosphate content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically⁷.

Results and Discussion

The results of uptake of cobalt by CaHA (synthetic and natural) is represented diagrammatically in Fig. 1. The uptake of Co²⁺ by CaHA was found to (i) decrease with increase of pH of the medium of equilibration in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, (ii) increase with increase of concentration of Co²⁺ and (iii) increase with decrease in particle size of CaHA. The uptake of Co²⁺ was found to be very rapid initially within the first 60 min (7.4 wt % for synthetic and 5.6 wt % for natural) and remained almost constant (Fig. 1a). The uptake was found to decrease from 16.26 wt % to 10.40 wt % with synthetic and from 12.8 wt % to 9.4 wt % with natural CaHA when the pH was decreased from 8.0 to 5.0 (Fig. 1b). It was also a linear function of increase from 3.6 wt % to 18.4 wt % for synthetic and from 3.2 wt % to 12.8 wt % for natural as the concentration of the medium of Co(NO₃)₂ solution increased from 0.01M to 0.1M (Fig. 1c). Fig. 1d shows that the uptake under a given set of experimental conditions increased from 12.8 wt % to 22.6 wt % with synthetic and 11.6 wt % to 18.8 wt % with natural CaHA when the mean radius of the particle decreased from 350μ to 60μ. The results of two experiments one at 35° and another at 100° are represented in (Fig. 1a) and it was found that the uptake of cobalt increases and reaches a maximum of 7.4 wt % with 60 minutes and thereafter remains constant probably due to the adsorption of cobalt on the surface of CaHA crystals in the first case and in second case it reaches up to 10.0 wt % of CaHA at 100° within 60 minutes and thereafter remains constant. This can be due to the subsequent

Fig. 1. Uptake of Cobalt by CaHA

diffusion of the adsorbed cobalt into the interior of the crystal lattice. Thus the uptake of Co^{2+} by CaHA at lower temperature is governed by adsorption while at higher temperature the process is adsorption-diffusion controlled.

Fig. 2. pH Dependence of solubility of Ca-CoHA

Results of incorporation of cobalt on solubility of the bone mineral is diagrammatically represented in Fig. 2. The dependence of solubility on (i) the pH of the medium of equilibration over physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 and (ii) the cobalt content in the sample at a given pH was investigated. It was observed that (i) the solubility of a given sample decreases with increase of pH of the dissolving medium (Fig. 2B) which is due to the protonation tendency of PO_4^{3-} in the dissolving medium⁷ and (ii) at a given pH the solubility increases with the cobalt content in the solid solution (Fig. 2A). This observation can be explained on the basis of (i) the common ion effect applied to solubility product of the solid solutions according to Milhofer⁹ and (ii) due to the formation of covalent bonds on the introduction of Co^{2+} in CaHA^{10} . This explains the role of incorporation of Co^{2+} in the solubility of the bone mineral.

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